

trap and the Robinson trap (see table). The Robinson trap may have trapped fewer midges because the high-intensity

light attracted many kinds of insects, including large ones, which made it difficult for fragile, smaller gall midges to reach

the trap. It also may be that the photokinetic response of gall midge is greater toward the infrared range. □

Brown planthopper biotypes in Korea

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Brown planthopper (BPH) populations come to Korea on prevailing low-pressure winds from southern China during the crop growing season. We studied the distribution of migrating BPH biotypes in Korea. Seventy-eight BPH females were collected from the southwest coast of the Korean peninsula 23-27 Aug 1982. They

were individually reared for two to three generations on susceptible rice variety Milyang 23 in the greenhouse.

Differential varieties were Milyang 23 with no resistance gene, Cheongcheongbyeon with *Bph 1* resistance gene, and Milyang 63 with *bph 2* resistance gene (see table).

BPH biotypes from each local collection were differentiated using the seedling bulk testing method. Results showed 61 local collections were BPH biotype 1, 8 were biotype 2, and 9 were biotype 3 (see figure). □

A simple technique for rearing rice thrips in the glasshouse

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Identification of varietal resistance to rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips (Baliothrips) biformis* (Bagnell) requires a mass screening technique that can be used in the glasshouse. We tested techniques for mass rearing rice thrips.

Rice seedlings heavily infested with thrips were uprooted from the field and planted in groups of 5 in shallow 15- × 27- × 6-cm plastic planting flats in the glasshouse. Each group of infested seedlings was surrounded by 4 groups of 1-week-old Bg 34-8 uninfested seedlings. Distance between seedling groups was 3-5 cm.

Thrips moved from the infested seedlings to the uninfested ones and reproduced. The colony was maintained by uprooting newly infested seedlings and planting new seedlings. A colony was successfully maintained for more than 4 months (about 6 generations) and each flat of infested seedlings could be used to infest 3 to 5 trays of uninfested seedlings. It took about 30 minutes to plant one flat of seedlings. □

Reaction of different rice varieties to BPH biotypes and local collections in Korea in 1982.

Variety	Resistance gene	Damage rating ^a					
		Biotype			Local collections from		
		1	2	3	Ashan	Hongseong	Boseong
Milyang 23	None	S	S	S	S	S	S
Cheongcheongbyeon	<i>Bph 1</i>	R	S	R	R	S	R
Milyang 63	<i>bph 2</i>	R	R	S	R	R	S

Based on seedling bulk test. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Distribution of brown planthopper biotypes in Korea.

Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) products for control of rice stem borers

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The insect antifeedant properties of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) oil seed are well known. In addition to phagodeterrence, insect growth-disrupting properties have also been attributed to several neem derivatives. Cake made from neem seeds after oil extraction has been reported to be an excellent insect repellent, organic

manure. and an effective nitrification inhibitor.

To verify these attributes of neem products, field trials conducted at Mbita Point Field Station of ICIPE in western Kenya used neem oil, neem cake, and blended urea-neem cake. Urea-neem cake is a mixture of 1,000 g urea fertilizer (46% N) to 250 g neem cake. Neem cake and urea-neem cake were incorporated in the subsoil at land preparation before transplanting at similar neem cake rates. Neem oil was sprayed on rice plants 1, 30, and 55 days after transplanting (DT). It was mixed with water and sprayed at 6, 15, and 30% emulsified concentration (EC), the equivalent of 10, 25, and 50 liters/ha, respectively. Sindano, a traditional rice variety, was grown without additional fertilizer.

During the trial, the predominant insect species were the white borer *Maliarpha separatella* and the pink borer *Sesamia calamistis*. *M. separatella* caused a large proportion of unfilled grains. *S. calamistis* caused whiteheads at plant maturity. The stalk-eyed fly *Diopsis thoracica* and *D. apicalis* infested rice at early vegetative phase and caused deadhearts.

Neem oil at high concentrations was better protection than neem cake or urea-neem cake at early vegetative stage. Plots treated with urea-neem cake had more deadhearts than those treated with neem cake, which showed that N induced

Effect of neem products on stem borer infestation and rice yield in western Kenya.^a

Treatment	Rate/ha	Insect infestation ^b			Yield components						
		Deadhearts (%)	Whiteheads (no./1000 tillers)	Stem infestation (%)	Harvest index ^c	Weight of filled grains per hill (g)					
Neem oil	10 liters	3.1	cd	.3	b	60	ab	42.1	a	31.9	ab
	25 -	2.0	de	.6	b	53	ab	42.8	ab	31.5	ab
	50 -	0.0	f	.8	b	51	ab	42.8	ab	38.8	b
Neem cake (NC)	10 kg	1.9	e	.5	b	49	b	42.8	ab	27.7	ab
	25 -	1.4	e	.5	b	49	b	43.5	b	44.2	bc
	50 -	2.8	d	.2	b	37	c	43.8	b	52.5	c
Urea-neem cake	50 - (10 kg NC + 40 kg urea)	4.4	b	.3	b	37	c	44.4	bc	35.3	b
Blended urea-neem cake mixture	125 - (25+100-)	3.5	c	1.1	ab	43	b	44.8	c	52.5	c
	250 - (50+200-)	2.6	d	.7	b	37	c	44.7	c	62.4	d
Untreated	0	8.5	a	4.5	a	69	a	41.5	a	21.6	a

^aMean of 3 replications of 12-m² plots each. Means in a column followed by common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDeadhearts: percent tillers with deadhearts at 60 DT, caused mainly by *Diopsis* spp. Whiteheads: number of whiteheads in 1,000 tillers at harvest; stem infestation: percent stem infested by *M. separatella*.

^cHarvest index = $\frac{\text{dry grain weight}}{\text{dry grain and straw weight}} \times 100$

Diopsis infestation and attenuated the systemic effect of neem cake (see table).

At harvest, percentage stem infestation of *M. separatella* was significantly lower in plots treated with neem cake and urea-neem cake than in untreated and neem-oil-treated plots. However, there was no significant difference in the number of whiteheads. Neem oil does not affect *M. separatella* infestation, probably because it has low persistence under sunshine and high temperature.

Crops treated with neem cake and

urea-neem cake had higher grain and straw weights than plots treated with low concentrations of neem oil and untreated plots. Results showed that combining neem cake and nitrogen fertilizer produces significantly higher yields. When rice stems were dissected at harvest, high larval mortality and delayed *M. separatella* development were observed in plots where neem cake or urea-neem cake was applied. The systemic effect of neem cake might be related to *M. separatella* mortality and low stem infestation.

Parasitization of gall midge maggots in exposed and suppressed galls

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Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* infestation causes galls, often called silvershoots. Infested plants compensate by producing excessive tillers that give the rice plant a bushy look. These tillers are unproductive and galls forming within them do not protrude through the leaf whorl, but harbor maggots parasitized by *Platygaster oryzae* (Cameron), an egg-larval parasite.

Rice workers scoring for varietal

1. Exposed and suppressed galls in Jaya, Bhubaneswar, India.